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EDITORIAL DESK

I wish to express my profound gratitude to Almighty God for the grace to successfully complete the volume 2 of the West African Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (WAJEAP).

The twelve articles were the products of well researched papers that were presented at the international conference held in May 2024 at the Presbyterian University of East Africa in Kikuyu, Nairobi, Kenya. The conference was well attended by over 25 universities across the globe. These published articles have been peer reviewed and plagiarism checks conducted on them before publication.

I, therefore, want to deeply appreciate the management team of the Presbyterian University of East Africa for making this publication a reality. All the writers and authors are congratulated for passing the stringent measures set by the guild of editors.

Congratulations to everyone.

Prof. M. O. B. Mohammed FNAEAP

Head, Editorial Team

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SCHOOL CLIMATE AND CONDITIONS OF SERVICE AS DETERMINANT OF TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between school climate and conditions of service as determinants of teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State. Two hypotheses (tested at 0.05 level of significance) and two research questions were set to serve as guides for the study. The study's foundation anchored is on Systems theory and Motivation theory. Correlational and descriptive research designs were adopted. The study population comprised 322 Principals, 644 Vice-principals, 966 heads of departments and 20,243 teachers in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State. The sample sizes were 96 Principals, 192 Vice-principals, 288 heads of departments and 960 teachers after stratifying the population into Education Districts and thereafter selecting through purposive and simple random sampling techniques. Three main instruments were used to collect data after ensuring their validity and establishing their reliability using the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient method. These included 'The School Climate Questionnaire (SCQ) ($r=0.890$), conditions of service Questionnaire (CSQ) ($r = 0.773$) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) ($r = 0.837$) Analysis of data was carried out using both descriptive and inferential statistics (Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient, Regression Analysis). Some of the findings were that a positive negligible and non-significant relationship exists between school climate and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria ($r = 0.008$, $p > 0.05$). A significant relationship exists between school climate and conditions of service. Furthermore, the results showed that a non-significant relationship exists among school climate, conditions of service and teachers' job performance ($\rho = 0.802 > 0.05$) in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study concluded that the higher the conditions of service, the more the school climate in public senior secondary schools and vice-versa. The study therefore recommended that Principals and School Authorities should make the school climate conducive for teachers to perform their duties well, Government and school management staff should ensure regular training and re-training of teachers through in-service training, seminars, conferences and workshops as part of conditions of service towards enhancing job performance. Government and school management should also motivate teachers with surprise packages such as soft loans, free medical care free accommodation etc. which will spur teachers to enhance their job performance.

Keywords: School climate, conditions of service, Teachers Job Performance, Public Senior Secondary Schools, Welfare Packages

INTRODUCTION

One goal of every organisation is to obtain maximum performance from members of the group, within the standard conditions outlined in the system. In the School system, for example, it is intended that teachers make their maximum contribution to ensure that the goals of the school are achieved and accomplished. However, a conducive school climate and favourable conditions of service are deemed to propel teachers to achieve school goals.

Meanwhile, a school is a formal organisation which consciously coordinates the activities of two or more people towards achieving a common goal (Abari & Mohammed, 2018).

The school is a social organisation with a unique formation that influences the behaviour of the human component. The human component in the school includes the students, teachers and administrators. Peretomode (2014) conceived the school as a social system involving two classes of phenomena that are independent and at the same interactive with the individual behaviour and the social behaviour in a social system.

The quality of a nation's educational sector depends considerably on teachers as well as on the collective interactions of the internal and external forces that intervene in the fulfilment of the purpose for setting up schools. The effectiveness and stability of the schools are mostly based on their school climate, conditions of service and the performance of teachers (Wentzel & Watkins, in Emu, 2018). Teachers are the backbone of an education activity, the success and failure of education activities highly depend on their performance (Muhammad, Rahmat & Malik, 2013). Meanwhile, job performance is defined as putting knowledge and skills into practice so that work can be done effectively and efficiently. Job performance is the duties carried out by teachers in the school which are aimed at achieving both education and school objectives (Griffing, 2012; Adejumobi 2018). In the words of Adejumobi and Ojikutu (2013), teachers' job performance is shown in terms of teachers' lesson presentation which ranges from the introduction of the lesson to teachers' mastery of the subject, interaction with the students, evaluation, conclusion and students' external examination. Teachers' performance can be determined or measured using several yardsticks such as their effectiveness in the delivery of lessons, writing of lesson notes, selection, and usage of instructional materials, completing several periods per week and scheme of work, as well as involvement and commitment to other duties that will lead to the realization of school goals. The success or failure of any educational programme then depends on the performance of teachers.

To achieve important objectives of secondary education, the school should be seen as a healthy place for learning, where the dreams and ambitions of students are achieved, teachers are motivated to give their best, where all are respected and feel connected with the school. The quality and character of school life or the overall characteristics and atmosphere in the school constitute the school climate. It is based on the school personnel's experiences of school life and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning practices (National School Climate Centre, 2017). Dorina, (2013) opined that school climate is the mixture of beliefs, values and behaviours of students, teaching staff, leaders and parents, level of independence, leadership styles and job satisfaction. School climate is subjective because it is based on perception. The school climate, as perceived by the teachers is the feelings of the teachers concerning the arrangement and the activities in the school as these relate to the extent they feel the arrangement, interaction and activities create a balance between the personnel needs and the school goals.

The school is influenced by formal organisations and informal organisations. The formal organisation is designed to ensure that all interactions lead towards the realization of the school goals, while the informal standpoint is the interaction that helps teachers satisfy their personal needs. Teachers' perception of how they feel, their morale and their commitment would form the perceived climate of the school (Akinlolu, 2019). In a nutshell, school climate refers to the feeling of teachers about the structure of the school as they work to balance the school goals and their personal goals. There are several factors which can determine how

teachers feel about their school. These include leadership style, a system of motivation, a communication network, class size and so on. The leadership pattern or style employed by the principal as the school administrator determines his/her attitudes and approaches to teachers. The attitude of principals towards encouraging the teachers by rewarding their hard work will also form the teachers' feelings about the school. Therefore, school climate can be perceived as the prevailing atmosphere in the school, which is mainly dictated by the leaders and affects the way teachers perceive their school and affects their values and attitudes towards school and work.

However, where the school climate becomes unfavourable, that is, where the school is not conducive and the principal's leadership is autocratic, this can affect teachers' job performance and students' learning outcomes. Yet, two of the principal agents in secondary school education - the principal and teachers should be more responsive and responsible in terms of the achievement of school goals. This is because the efficiency of a school system depends to a large extent on how human and material resources are motivated and effectively utilized within a conducive school to enhance teachers' job performance. Research has shown that teachers - as individuals and schools - as units of instruction, can produce extraordinary learning, if all relevant variables, classified under school characteristics (effective school leadership, high levels of collaboration and communication, a supportive learning environment that is conducive and healthy) are present (Wagner & Davis, in Adejumbi, 2013). These relevant variables cumulate in what could be referred to as conditions of service for the teachers.

According to the Adejumbi, (2013), conditions of service are that part of employment that set out the duties, responsibilities, hours of work, salary increment, staff development, leave benefits and other privileges to be enjoyed by a person employed. However, in any organisation or system, staff welfare is an indispensable tool in enhancing the productivity of workers towards organisational goals and the school is not left out. The condition of service is favourable to teachers when teachers are well pleased with their job and they will deliver their duties effectively and efficiently (Kayode, in Akinlolu, 2019).

Statement of problem

Teachers constitute a human resource that makes school and educational objectives a reality. The failure or success of educational activities highly depends on teachers' job performance. Despite government and school management efforts to enhance effectiveness and efficiency among teachers in public senior secondary schools, however, there seem to be challenges such as overcrowded classrooms which may impinge upon the school with the ratio of 1:100 instead of the expected ratio of 1:40 in some public senior secondary schools in Lagos state Nigeria (FRN 2013), also as observed by Ogundare (2018). The autocratic leadership style of some public school principals, lack of collaboration and interpersonal relationships among teachers and colleagues, teachers and principals, teachers and students, teachers and parents are also characteristics of the school that present a climate that may hinder the adequate performance of teachers.

Furthermore, the conditions of service in terms of the salary scale in comparison with teachers' counterparts in other professions, lack of accommodation for teachers, irregular promotion, irregular leave, poor welfare package and inadequate training may affect teachers' job performance. This is evident from a high rate of teachers' turnover, teachers' absenteeism, the non-challant attitude of teachers in carrying out their duties, indiscipline and dissatisfaction among teachers.

Purpose of the Study

1. Investigate the relationship that exists between school climate and conditions of service in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria.
2. Examine the relationship among school climate, conditions of service and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- Does a relationship exist between school climate and conditions of service in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria?
- Is there any relationship among school climate, conditions of service and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between school climate and conditions of service in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship among school climate, conditions of service and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

To ascertain the degree to which data collected from the SCQ, CSQ and TJPQ consistently measure what they purport to measure, the instruments were subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Test. The questionnaires were administered to 60 teachers, 18 heads of departments, 12 Vice principals and 6 Principals who were part of the population of the study but not part of the sample. Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Analysis was used to determine the reliability of this School Climate Questionnaire (SCQ), Conditions of service Questionnaire (CSQ) for teachers and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) for school leaders. The Coefficients obtained were 0.890 for School Climate, 0.773 for Conditions of Service and 0.837 for Teachers' Job Performance. Thus, the questionnaires were found substantially reliable. Data collected were analysed using both descriptive statistics (percentages, tables, figures, charts, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics used to test the hypothesis. Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) analysis was used to test hypothesis 1, Regression analysis was used to test hypothesis 2 all at 0.05 level of significance. All analyses were carried out using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 24.

FINDINGS

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between school climate and conditions of service in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria.

To test the hypothesis, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Analysis was conducted between school climate and conditions of service. The scores of responses on items of school climate were computed and used as a single variable to correlate the sum of scores on items of conditions of service. The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between school climate and conditions of service in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria

		School climate	Condition of service
School climate	Pearson Correlation	1	0.477**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.001
	N	933	933
Condition of service	Pearson Correlation	0.477**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	
	N	933	933

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result in Table 1 shows that there is a positive, weak and significant relationship between school climate and conditions of service in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria ($r = 0.477, \rho < 0.05$). This implies that the higher the conditions of service, the more conducive the school climate in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria, and vice-versa. The result suggests that conditions of service do significantly influence school climate in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between school climate and conditions of service in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria is hereby rejected. No discussion and support/opposition with literature?

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship among school climate, conditions of service and teachers’ job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, multiple regression analysis was used. Data collected on school climate, conditions of service and teachers’ job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria were therefore subjected to multiple regression analysis and the results of the analysis are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship among school climate, conditions of service and teachers’ job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.031 ^a	0.001	-0.003	8.79257

a. Predictors: (Constant), Condition of service, School climate

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	34.126	2	17.063	0.221	0.802 ^b
	Residual	35871.531	464	77.309		
	Total	35905.657	466			

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers job performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Condition of service, School climate

Table 2 presents the ANOVA results on the relationship among school climate, conditions of service and teachers’ job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State,

Nigeria. The results show that there is a positive relationship among school climate, conditions of service and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.031. The relationship among school climate, conditions of service and teachers' job performance is slight. Furthermore, the results suggest that a non-significant relationship exists among school climate, conditions of service and teachers' job performance ($\rho = 0.802 > 0.05$) in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship among climate, conditions of service and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria is not rejected.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion can be drawn from this study that the higher the conditions of service, the more conducive the school climate in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria, and vice-versa. Conditions of service do not necessarily make teachers perform their jobs in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. It can also be concluded from the study that school climate and conditions of service might not be factors in teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The school climate is part of the conditions of service as it provides the environment in which the teachers work. Meanwhile, the three variables are interrelated and interdependent, school climate relates to conditions of service and conditions of service relating to teachers' job performance in public senior secondary in Lagos state, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made.

1. Principals and school authorities should make the school climate conducive for teachers to perform their duties well.
2. The Government has to look at the conditions of service critically to improve teachers' job performance.
3. The government should continuously improve the school climate to provide a conducive atmosphere for teachers to perform their duties.
4. The government and school management staff should ensure regular training and re-training of teachers through in-service training, seminars, conferences and workshops towards enhancing school climate, conditions of service and job performance.
5. The government and school management should motivate teachers with surprise packages such as soft loans, free medical care, free accommodation etcetera which will spur them to enhance their job performance.

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